

Mechanical Properties of Natural Fibre-based Woven Fabric-reinforced Thermoplastic and Thermoset Composites

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Abstract:

This study evaluates the mechanical properties of jute and flax woven fabric-reinforced composites in both thermoplastic and thermoset matrices. This investigation examines the impact of natural fibres (jute and flax) as well as the influence of matrix materials (thermoplastic and thermoset), on the mechanical behaviour of advanced composites. A comprehensive suite of mechanical tests, including tensile, flexural, and impact assessments, were conducted to evaluate critical properties such as strength, stiffness, toughness, and durability. The results revealed that under quasi-static loads such as tensile and flexural tests, thermoset woven composites exhibited outstanding load bearing performance, while thermoplastic composites showed exceptional resistance to dynamic impact forces.

Keywords: Co-wrapped yarn, mechanical properties, natural fibers, thermoplastic, thermoset

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1. Introduction

Recent research has been focused on developing eco-friendly and sustainable natural fiber-reinforced polymer composites (NFPCs) as alternatives to synthetic ones. Natural fibers, derived from renewable resources such as flax, jute, hemp, and kenaf, have gained prominence as reinforcing elements due to their inherent advantages such as low density, biodegradability, and renewability [1-3]. When interwoven into matrices, they contribute to the formation of composites that exhibit remarkable strength-to-weight ratios and enhanced sustainability profiles. The matrix choice, whether thermoplastic or thermoset, introduces a crucial dimension to the performance and processing characteristics of these composites [4-5].

The characteristics of composites are primarily influenced by three key elements: the type of reinforcement, the polymer form, and the interface between them. Polymers are divided into two groups: thermoplastics and thermosets. Thermoplastics are preferred when ductility and toughness are required, as they can be reversibly reshaped with changes in temperature and pressure. However, thermoplastics generally exhibit lower creep resistance at elevated temperatures compared to thermosets. Common thermoplastic matrix materials used in polymer composites include polypropylene, nylon, polycarbonate, and polyethylene. On the other hand, thermosets require a curing process during composite fabrication and cannot be re-melted or reformed after curing. They are characterized by brittleness, dimensional stability, and rigidity. Epoxy, polyester, and polyimides are examples of thermoset materials [6-10].

However, compared to thermoset matrix composites, thermoplastic matrix composites face challenges during the impregnation process due to their higher melt viscosity. This difficulty in impregnating the textile reinforcement structure with the thermoplastic matrix can lead to insufficient composite properties [11-13]. To address this issue and improve the impregnation process prior to consolidation, hybrid yarns can be employed in the production of the preforms. The use of hybrid yarns allows for better control and distribution of the thermoplastic matrix within the reinforcement structure, resulting in improved composite properties [14-16].

Despite significant progress in the development of woven-based thermoplastic and thermoset composites using diverse fiber types, there is a need for a thorough characterization of these composites, focusing specifically on the utilization of various natural fibers. Furthermore, the literature on fabric preforms made from cowrap spinning yarns is currently limited. Therefore, there is a crucial need in understanding the implications of hybrid yarns on the performance of thermoplastic composites reinforced with natural fibers that requires further exploration.

In this study, the mechanical behaviour of thermoset and thermoplastic resins is investigated with a specific focus on evaluating the influence of various natural fibers, such as jute and flax. To facilitate this investigation, cowrap spinning yarns were manufactured using a hollow spindle spinning machine, wherein polypropylene (PP) filament enveloped jute and flax rovings. The PP filaments functioned as carriers for the natural fibers throughout the processing stages and eventually transformed into the polymer matrix in the final composites. This approach not only alleviated challenges related to impregnation but also safeguarded the reinforcing natural fibers from potential damage during the processing steps.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The natural fiber yarns utilized in this research were Jute, sourced from Gloster Ltd., Kolkata, and Flax, obtained from Jaya Shree Textiles, Rishra. Both Jute and Flax yarns had a linear density of 600 tex. A comprehensive breakdown of the properties of various reinforcement fibers is presented in Table 1. For crafting hybrid reinforcements and developing hybrid dry-woven fabrics, the thermoplastic matrix fiber employed was 840-denier Polypropylene (PP) multifilament, procured from Fitpack Textile Mills Ltd. The thermoset resin selected for the study was Lapox ARL-125 epoxy, paired with AH-367 curing agent as the hardener.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of reinforcement fibers

Fibre	Linear Density [Tex]	Density [g/cm ³]	Diameter [μm]	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Elongation at break (%)
Flax	600	1.4-1.5	40-600	250-700	40-70	2.7-3.3
Jute	600	1.3-1.5	25-200	200-600	10-30	2-3

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Preparation of the Reinforcement/PP Hybrid Yarns

Hybrid yarns combining Reinforcement and PP were generated through the co-wrapping technique employing a hollow spindle spinning machine. The Reinforcement roving, having a pre-determined linear density, underwent processing through a roving condenser and inactive drafting rollers. Simultaneously, the PP filament, drawn from a package mounted on the hollow spindle, traversed through the spindle, enveloping the reinforcement roving at its core. The high rotational speed of the spindle induced pseudo-twist in both the reinforcement roving and PP filament. As illustrated in Figure 1, after passing through the twisting hook, the pseudo-twist in the reinforcement roving was eliminated, while the twist in the PP filament wraps was retained. A meticulous execution of this process ensured a consistent fiber volume fraction of 50% ± 5%. The resulting hybrid yarns, termed co-wrapped yarns (CWYs), were created by wrapping polypropylene (PP) filament around flax and jute rovings. These CWYs, characterized by shortened impregnation periods and reduced resin flow distances during processing, exhibit potential for the cost-effective production of intricately shaped composite parts.

Figure 1. Manufacturing Process of Hybrid Reinforcement by Wrap Spinning

2.2.2 Preparation of two-dimensional (2D) woven fabrics

2D woven fabrics with plain weave design were developed on the customized rapier weaving loom at Focus Incubation Centre at Indian Institute of Technology Delhi. Ends per inch and picks per inch were calculated in a way so that constant areal density can be achieved. Subsequently, four layers of 2D woven fabrics were sequentially arranged, following a 0-90° sequence.

2.2.3 Manufacturing of thermoplastic composites

The thermoplastic composites were fabricated through the compression moulding technique. Utilizing their corresponding 2D woven preforms of flax and jute designated as TPF2DFRC and TPJ2DFRC respectively. The 2D woven preform was positioned within the mould, enveloped with Teflon sheets at both the top and bottom, and underwent processing in a compression moulding machine. The processing conditions involved subjecting the composites to a temperature of 185°C and 10 MPa pressure for duration of 10 minutes full press heating and 10 minutes cooling, as shown in figure 2. The maintained thickness for all thermoplastic composites ranged between 2.5 to 3 mm.

Figure 2. Manufacturing Process of 2D woven fabric-based thermoplastic composites

The creation of 2D woven fabric-reinforced composites (2DFRCs) utilizing 2D weaving preforms of flax and jute, named as TSF2DFRC and TSJ2DFRC respectively, was achieved through vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM). The optimal resin-to-hardener ratio, established at 100:32, was determined through the optimization of mechanical attributes using the same resin material. To eliminate any air bubbles, the resin-hardener mixture underwent de-airing in a desiccator through two two-minute cycles before impregnation. The

VARTM process for producing 2DFRCs is illustrated in Figure 3. Subsequently, the samples underwent vacuum curing for 24 hours at 25°C post resin infusion to attain a high level of handling strength.

Figure 3: Manufacturing Process of 2D woven fabric-based thermoset composites

2.2.5 Characterization of mechanical properties of 2D woven structural composites

2.2.5.1 Tensile test

The tensile testing was carried out using ZwickRoell Z250 UTMin accordance with ASTM D3039 standards. The test speed was maintained at 2 mm/min, with a force shutdown threshold set at 80% of F_{max} . The load-cell employed had a capacity of 250 kN, and the sample dimensions were 200 mm x 25 mm. The upper force limit was capped at 100 kN, and gauge length was 100 mm. Gripping attachment was pneumatic in nature.

2.2.5.2 Flexural (3-point bending) test

The flexural testing was carried out using ZwickRoell Z250 UTMin accordance with the ASTM D7264 standards. The test speed was maintained at 2 mm/min, with a force shutdown threshold set at 80% of F_{max} . A 25kN load-cell was employed, and the span-to-thickness ratio was 32:1. The upper force limit was restricted to 100 kN, while the specimen width measured 13 mm. Gripping attachment was pneumatic in nature.

2.2.5.3 Edgewise impact test

The edgewise impact test was performed using an Izod Impact (Pendulum type) instrument, following the ASTM D256 standard. The impact velocity was set at 3.5 m/sec, with the pendulum energy and mass measuring 11 Joules and 1.84 kg, respectively. The angle of release was precisely set at 147.96°. Sample dimensions for this test were 64 mm x 12.7 mm, with a notch depth length of 2 mm and a notch angle of 45°.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Tensile behavior of thermoplastic and thermoset woven composites

Initially, TPJ2DFRC exhibited a higher tensile modulus in the elastic regime compared to TPF2DFRC, maintaining this superiority until a slight deviation occurred at approximately 2.5% strain. Beyond this point, both curves transitioned into the hardening phase. Beyond this point, both curves transitioned into the hardening phase, with strain continuing to increase at a reduced pace compared to the elastic range, ultimately reaching a maximum of 4.4%. Subsequently, a distinct region emerged, marked by a gradual reduction in hardness as the composite experienced strain failure at 5.4%. Due to its inherently low tensile strength, TPJ2DFRC witnessed fiber fracture shortly after reaching peak stress. In contrast, TPF2DFRC exhibited enhanced performance beyond the elastic regime. The resilience of Flax fiber against longitudinal force sustained a strain of 12.7% at tensile strength, breaking immediately after reaching peak force at 13.22% strain at break.

The thermoset composites demonstrated a lower strain percentage, attributed to their brittle failure nature, in contrast to the thermoplastic composites. Flax fibers exhibited a relatively better load-bearing ability than Jute fibers in this context. This emphasizes the overall superior mechanical performance of thermoset composites in

terms of tensile properties. This superior performance can be due to thermoset matrices' specific properties, such as enhanced interphase bonding and stiffness, contributing to improved stress distribution along the longitudinal axis. While thermoset composites' inherent brittleness affects their strain %, paradoxically, it results in a more controllable and efficient load-bearing mechanism.

In comparison, despite their advantages in ease of processing and impact resistance, thermoplastic composites tend to exhibit limitations in terms of longitudinal load-bearing capacity. The polymer chains in thermoplastics allow for greater flexibility, but this can compromise their ability to efficiently transmit and distribute loads in the longitudinal direction, leading to reduced load-bearing performance. Understanding these details is essential for material selection in applications where longitudinal load-bearing capacity is important. For applications requiring longitudinal strength and stability, thermoset composites surpass thermoplastic composites due to their superior mechanical qualities.

When comparing the two natural fibers, it becomes apparent that flax fiber is more suitable for structural applications, primarily because of its superior tensile properties.

Figure 4: Tensile behavior of thermoplastic and thermoset woven composites

3.2 Flexural behavior of thermoplastic and thermoset woven composites

The Jute-based woven composite demonstrated a superior strain percentage at flexural strength compared to the Flax counterpart. It is worth noting that although the Jute-reinforced thermoplastic composite had lower overall flexural strength, it exhibited a greater strain capacity at maximum bending stress. The findings here emphasize the intricate relationship between fiber type and flexural performance, providing valuable insights into how the material behaves when subjected to bending loads. This knowledge can assist in selecting the most suitable material for specific applications. Flax-based thermoplastic composite (TPF2DFRC) demonstrates the higher Flexural Modulus and Flexural Strength, indicating superior stiffness and strength. On the other hand, Jute-based thermoplastic composite (TPJ2DFRC) exhibits relatively lower values, suggesting a more flexible nature. The Flexure-strain at Break with jute-based composite (TPJ2DFRC) reflects the material's deformation capacity before failure.

Comparing the flexural properties of Flax-based thermoset composite (TSF2DFRC) to Jute (TSJ2DFRC) reinforcements, the thermoset composites showcased superior flexural performance. Thermoset composites, particularly in tension mode, exhibited exceptional flexural properties compared to their thermoplastic counterparts, highlighting their increased ability to withstand heavy loads. The higher stiffness of thermoset composites necessitates greater stress for fracture under flexural loads, contributing to enhanced overall strength and durability. Despite the inherent fragility of the matrix, thermoset composites demonstrated improved flexural properties when compared to thermoplastic alternatives, attributed to the robust interphase between fibers and matrix, as well as the overall stiffness of the material.

Figure 5: Flexural behavior of thermoplastic and thermoset woven composites

3.3 Izod impact behavior of thermoplastic and thermoset woven composites

The observed superior pendulum impact resistance in thermoplastic woven composites can be ascribed to their distinct mechanical behavior, showcasing their ability to deform and absorb energy through plastic deformation. This behavior is inherent to thermoplastics and contrasts with the typically brittle nature of thermoset counterparts. The unique molecular structure of thermoplastics allows them to undergo plastic deformation, enabling precise energy absorption during impact events. Thermoplastics can rearrange their molecules without any permanent chemical changes, facilitating effective energy dissipation.

In contrast, thermoset woven composites are generally more brittle due to their cross-linked and rigid molecular structures. When subjected to impact forces, the possibility of limited plastic deformation increases, potentially leading to catastrophic failure characterized by crack propagation and fragmentations. Flax composites showed better impact resistance than jute counterparts due to its superior tensile properties, which outperform jute yarns.

Figure 6: Izod impact behavior of thermoplastic and thermoset woven composites

4. Conclusions

This study sought to examine the relationship between matrix properties and the mechanical performance of natural fiber-reinforced composites. Thermoset composites demonstrated exceptional performance over thermoplastics in low-strain rate (quasi-static) mechanical tests. On the other hand, thermoplastic composites have shown remarkable resilience when it comes to edgewise dynamic impact properties. Flax-based structures demonstrated exceptional mechanical properties compared to jute fibers. These findings contribute valuable

insights into the intricate relationship between matrix properties and the overall mechanical performance of natural fiber-reinforced composites.

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